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Classification of Voltage Sag due to Faults and Induction Motor Starting

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ABSTRACT

This paper focus on events, that causes a temporary decrease in the magnitude of voltage at power frequency. The paper aims at characterization of voltage sags due to faults and induction motor starting. The modified IEEE distribution system is considered for study and same is simulated using PSCAD. The signals for features extraction are processed using Wavelet transform. The Statistical parameters computed from detailed level 4 (D-4) are used as an input to classifier. Multilayer perceptron network is used as a classifier to differentiate the cause behind the voltage sag.

Keywords:- Simulation, Power Quality, Voltage Sag, Power System Faults, Wavelet Transform, Neural Network

INTRODUCTION

For the satisfactory operation of end use devices, the utility is expected to supply undistorted, sinusoidal rated voltage continuously at rated frequency to the end users. A power quality problem can be defined as “any problem manifested in voltage, current, or frequency deviations that results in failure or mal-operation of end user equipment”.

Over the last decade voltage sag gains a serious concern amongst the utility, end users, equipment manufacturers as well as researchers. Voltage sag is a power quality problem that is prevalent in any power system. Voltage sag have attracted a lot of attention due to the problems that causes failure to equipment like adjustable speed drives, computers, industrial control systems etc.

The main causes of voltage sag are due to faults and large rating induction motor starting. Modern power electronic devices or equipment’s are sensitive to voltage variations and susceptible to damage. Because modern equipment has become more sensitive to voltage sags, maintaining good power quality has become increasingly important.

Ozgur Gencer et al. [1] , a new voltage sag detection method based on wavelet transform is developed. The work presents a reliable and implementation-friendly method for voltage sag detection. The method uses discrete wavelet transforms to determine beginning and ending of the voltage sag with sag magnitude. WT are essentially applied to extract information and as a basis for signal representation to achieve both good time and frequency position. The discrete wavelet transform (DWT) is used to identify rapid variations in voltage signals, enabling time-based localization of different frequency components using suitable wavelets. It offers enough information for both

analyzing and reconstructing the original signal, while also reducing the overall computation time.

In Tulasi Ram, et al. [2], described a wavelet transform is proposed to identify the power quality disturbance at its instance of occurrence. Power quality disturbances such as voltage sag, swell, interruptions, DC offset, frequency variations, and harmonics are analyzed and decomposed up to four levels using the Db4 wavelet. For certain types of disturbances, a second- or third-level decomposition is sufficient for accurate detection. The exact location of the disturbance can also be found on the time scale.

In paper Memon, et al. [3], described detection of PQ disturbances must be carried out first. PQ disturbances have been defined into several categories and software based novel approach techniques for detection of PQ disturbances by time and frequency analysis with wavelet transform is proposed. These techniques effectively identify waveform distortion–related power quality issues and offer a promising approach for addressing various electrical power quality problems.

Santoso. S, et al. [4], presents a new approach to detect, localize, and investigate the feasibility of classifying various types of power quality disturbances. The method is built on wavelet transform analysis, with a focus on the dyadic-orthonormal wavelet transform. The main concept is to break down the disturbance signal into components that capture both the smoothed and detailed features of the original waveform.

This is achieved through multi resolution signal decomposition. The authors demonstrate and validate their approach using real power-line disturbance data to detect and pinpoint various events. Based on the detection and localization outcomes,

they also make an initial attempt to determine how effectively different types of power quality disturbances can be uniquely identified.

Julio Barros et al. [5] presents an extensive literature review of the application of wavelet transforms in the detection and analysis of voltage events and provides a short description of the different methods proposed. Wavelet analysis offers simultaneous time–frequency information, making it particularly useful for analyzing voltage events. With the wavelet transform, high-frequency components of the signal are captured with fine time resolution, while low-frequency components are represented with coarser time resolution.

Paper [6] deals with the use of wavelet analysis and neural systems as a new tool for the analysis of power system disturbances, disturbances are automatically detected, compacted, and classified. In this work, a WT approach is proposed to detect and classify various types of power systems disturbances. A neural classification system using wavelet analysis has been used to distinguish Power system disturbances. This work leads us to believe that wavelet analysis together with neural structure, as a new tool, offers a great potential for

diagnosis of electrical power systems in the area of power quality problems.

S. suja et al.[7] discussed the power signal disturbances are detected using discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and categorized using neural networks. DWT is employed to capture the time of transient occurrence and extract frequency features of power disturbances. The coefficients obtained from DWT are further subjected to statistical manipulations for increasing the detection accuracy. PNN is used to classify disturbance type. The wavelet neural classifier along with the statistical computation has increased the classification accuracy

Paper [8], deals with the use of a continuous wavelet transforms to detect and analyze voltage sags and transients. A refined recursive algorithm is used to compute the time–frequency representation of electrical disturbances. The characteristics of each signal are evaluated on this time–frequency plane. By comparing the extracted features with predefined benchmark values, the method can detect the presence of disturbances and identify their specific types. It also estimates key parameters of voltage sags, including their duration and magnitude.

SYSTEM UNDER STUDY

Fig.1:-The modified IEEE distribution test feeder.

The details of the system under study are as follows:

Busses:

Bus 1: 12.47 kV, Bus 2: 12.47 kV,

Bus 3: 0.48 kV, Bus 4: 0.48 kV

Transmission Lines TLine1, TLine2:

Steady state frequency: 50Hz

Length: 5 Km

Number of conductors: 3

Transformers:

T1: Three phase, star/star, 50Hz, 12MVA, 115 kV/12.47 kV.

T2, T3: Three phase, star/star, 50Hz, 1.0MVA, 12.47kV/0.48kV

Induction motor:

Wound rotor induction motor

Rated power = 1.615 [MW]

Rated voltage [L-L] = 12.47 [kV]

Load at:

Bus 2: 0.30 MW, 0.15 MVAR, and 12.47 kV

Bus 3: 0.15 MW, 0.05 MVAR, and 0.48 kV

Bus 4: 0.10 MW, 0.05 MVAR, and 0.48 kV

Fig.2:-Simulation faults in PSCAD

Fig.3:-Simulation of Induction Motor Starting in PSCAD

Figure 2 and 3 shows a single line diagram of the system simulated in PSCAD for LG faults and induction motor starting. The study is carried out on BUS1 of the sample test system.

WAVELET TRANSFORM

The wavelet transform represents signal as a sum of wavelets at different locations (positions) and scales (duration). The wavelet coefficients work as weights of the wavelets to represent the signal at these locations and scales.

The Discrete Wavelet Transform:

The Discrete Wavelet (DWT), is used to decompose a discretized signal into different resolution levels. It maps a sequence of numbers into a different sequence of numbers.

The discrete wavelet transform DWT provides sufficient information both for analysis and the synthesis of the original signal, with a significant reduction in the computation time. The DWT provides a time and frequency representation of the recorded power quality signals.

This is a very attractive feature in analyzing time series because time localization of spectral components can be obtained. Classical methods of signal processing depend on an underlying notion of stationary, for which methods such as Fourier analysis are very well adapted. In power quality researches, however, more properties other than stationary are required, and thus make the DWT application more appropriate than Fourier transform.

Wavelet Families:

There are a number of basic functions that can be used as the mother wavelet for Wavelet Transformation. Since the mother wavelet produces all wavelet functions used in the transformation through translation and scaling, it determines the characteristics of the resulting Wavelet Transform.

Fig 4: illustrates some of the commonly used wavelet functions. Haar wavelet is one of the oldest and simplest wavelet. Daubechies wavelets are the most popular wavelets. They represent the foundations of wavelet signal processing and are used in numerous applications.

The Haar, Daubechies, Symlets and Coiflets are compactly supported orthogonal wavelet. The wavelets are chosen based on their shape and their ability to analyze the signal in a

particular application. These wavelets along with Meyer wavelets are capable of perfect reconstruction. This paper uses Daubechies-4(db4) method for feature extraction.

Fig.4:- Wavelet families (a) Haar (b) Daubechies4 (c) Coiflet1 (d) Symlet2 (e) Meyer (f) Morlet (g) Mexican Hat

MULTILAYER PERCEPTRON

Fig.5:-Architecture of ANN

MLP is a powerful system, often capable of modeling complex, relationships between variables. It allows prediction of an output object for a given input object. The architecture of MLP is a layered feed forward neural network in which the non-linear elements (neurons) are arranged in successive layers, and the information flow is unidirectional from input layer to output layer through hidden layers.

An MLP with just one hidden layer can learn to approximate virtually any function to any degree of accuracy. For this reason MLPs are known as universal approximates and can be used when there is little prior knowledge of the relationship between input and targets.

The standard deviation is calculated as

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu)^2}$$

Where, μ is the mean of x , σ is the standard deviation of x

Mean value (μ) is calculated as

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

Energy: The energy of the signal is calculated as

$$E_x = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |X(n)|^2$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Time Domain Approach:

[1] Voltage sags due to faults

The voltage sags is observed in the system voltage due to the creation of different faults like LG, LLG, LLLG. The faults are created in the circuit by using timed fault logic for specifying the instant of fault and the duration. The study has been conducted on BUS1.

At BUS1 voltmeter E_a is connected for measuring the bus voltage. It has been observed that the voltage sag occurs between the times a fault initiates. The voltage sag remains till recovery of fault. After recovery of fault, normal value of voltage is obtained. The other buses i.e. BUS1, BUS2, BUS3, BUS4 are also affected.

One hidden layer is always sufficient provided enough data is present.

STATISTICAL PARAMETERS

The statistical parameters used in the study are discussed as follows.

Maximum value: The maximum value attained by a signal i.e. it refers to maximum signal point value of given sample.

Standard deviation: Standard deviation is the square root of the arithmetic average of the squares of the deviations measured from the mean i.e. it is a measure of the dispersion of a set of data from its mean. The more spread apart the data, the higher the deviation.

[A] LG fault

In this case fault is created in phase c to ground. It has been observed there is sag in only one phase i.e. (in phase c).

[B] LLG fault

In this case fault is created in phase A and C along with the ground. From fig.6(b), it has been observed there is sag in two phase and magnitude of voltage magnitude is reduced i.e. voltage sag is obtained.

[C] LLLG fault

Voltage sag due to LLLG fault as shown in fig. 6(c).It has been observed there is sag in three phases A, B and C along with the ground. The magnitude of voltage is reduced i.e. voltage sag obtained.

Fig.6(a):- Voltage sag due to LG fault

Fig.6(b):-Voltage sag due to LLG fault

Fig.6(c):-Voltage sag due to LLLG fault

Fig.6(d):- Voltages sag due to induction motor starting

[2] Voltage sags due to induction motor starting

The voltage magnitude is reduced i.e. voltage sag is obtained. This voltage sag is symmetrical: all three phases drop equally and then recover gradually in a similar way because the starting current of the motor is the same for all three phases.

The signals obtained from PSCAD are further analyzed using wavelet transform. The wavelet transform decomposed the signal up to six decomposition levels using db4 wavelet. The decomposition gives approximations and detailed coefficients. The decomposed signal for voltage sags due to different faults like LG, LLG, LLLG and induction motor starting are as shown below.

WAVELET TRANSFORM FOR FEATURE EXTRACTION:

[1] Wavelet decomposition of signal for voltage sags due to faults

Fig.7(a):- Wavelet decomposition of signal of voltage sag due to LG fault

Fig.7(b):- Wavelet decomposition of signal of voltage sag due to faults

Fig.7(c):- Voltage sag due to LLLG fault

Fig.7 (d):- Wavelet decomposition of signal of voltage sag due to induction motor starting.

[A] LG fault

Fig.7 (a) shows the original signal and wavelet decomposition of waveforms of voltage signal up to sixth level of LG fault i.e. (phase c to ground fault).

The original signal shows the voltage sag due to LG fault. The effect of LG fault can be more clearly visualized in D4 level.

[B] LLG fault

Fig.7 (b) shows the original signal and wavelet decomposition of waveforms of voltage signal up to sixth level of LLG fault. Here fault involves phase A and phase C along with the ground.

[C] LLLG fault

Fig.7(c) shows the original signal and wavelet decomposition of waveforms of voltage signal up to sixth level of LLLG

fault. Here fault involves all the three phases A, B and C along with the ground. The original signal shows the voltage sag due to LLLG fault. The effect of LLLG fault can be more clearly visualized in D4 level.

[2] Wavelet decomposition of signal of Voltage sag due to starting of induction motor

The wavelet decomposition of waveforms of voltage signal up to sixth level using Db4 wavelet of induction motor starting is shown in fig.7(d). From wavelet transform approach, classification of voltage sag due to faults and induction motor starting are not possible by visual inspection.

Because of this drawback various statistical parameters such as maximum value, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis and energy are calculated.

STATISTICAL PARAMETERS APPROACH:

Fig.8(a):-Maximum value of detailed coefficient at level 4

Fig.8(b):-Standard deviation of detailed coefficient at level 4

Fig.8(c):-Energy of detailed coefficient at level 4 for voltage

The detailed coefficient at level 4 obtained from DWT is further subjected to various statistical parameters for increasing the detection accuracy. The statistical parameter such as maximum value, std. deviation and energy are computed. Fig.8 (a)-8(c) shows the graphs of various statistical parameters for voltage sags due to different faults like LG, LLG, LLLG and induction motor starting of detailed coefficient at level 4. It has been observed that the magnitude for LG

and LLLG fault is near about same. From fig.8 (b), it has been observed that the magnitude of LG and LLLG fault is same.

From six different statistical parameters, maximum value, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis and energy. It is clear that with the help of visual inspection of various statistical parameters of voltage sags due to different faults and induction motor starting is not an easy task to classify.

RESULT OBTAINED FROM ANN

Fig.9:-Effect of number of processing element on classification accuracy for energy parameters by using MLP

As discussed in previous section the classification is not possible with visual inspection of statistical parameters hence ANN is used in order to classify the reasons behind the voltage sag. When energy as input is given to Multilayer perceptron network it gives 100% classification of events considered in the study.

The fig.9 indicates that when number of processing element is taken as 14, then 100% accuracy is obtained. The voltage sag classification is performed for different faults like LG, LLG, LLLG and induction motor starting. Hence, the classification of voltage sags due to faults and induction motor starting is done by using ANN

technique from which there is 100% accuracy.

CONCLUSION

The modified IEEE distribution test feeder System is simulated in PSCAD. The data obtained from simulation is in time domain. With the help of magnitude of voltage and duration of events, the cause of voltage sags cannot discriminate properly.

Hence in order to obtain correct classification the Wavelet - ANN approach is used. MLP for energy parameter gives 100% results i.e. 100% classification of voltage sags due to various types of faults and induction motor starting.

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